

IMPROVING CENTRAL LINE HANDLING PERFORMANCE IN CRITICAL CARE NURSES USING NURSE-LED INTERVENTION: A REVIEW ARTICLE

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Abstract

Background: A central line is used for various purposes, including measuring central venous pressure, administering medication and fluids, and transfusing blood, particularly in critically ill patients. The quality of central line handling after insertion has a direct impact on patient complications, as well as the acquisition of hospital-associated infections (HAIs). Educational and practice sessions have been proposed as an intervention to enhance the central line handling.

Objectives: This review critically evaluates and synthesizes existing literature on the effectiveness of nurse-led interventions while handling the central line by critical care nurses.

Methods and Materials: A comprehensive literature search was conducted across multiple databases, including CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Science Direct. Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT) and a publication date filter from 2018 to 2025 were applied.

Results: Evidence from reviewed studies demonstrates that the use of Nurse-Led interventions significantly improves patients' serious complications, including hematoma, thrombosis, pneumothorax, and hospital-associated infection. These evidence-based studies correlate to effective outcomes of patients, including decreased hospital stay, mortality, and morbidity & also decreased rate of central line-associated bloodstream infection.

INTRODUCTION

The central venous catheter (CVC) was introduced in 1929 by German surgical resident Werner Forssmann [1]. The CVC can be used for various purposes, including administering medicine and fluid, measuring central venous pressure (CVP), and blood transfusion in critically ill patients [1]. Furthermore, the right internal Jugular (IJ) is larger in diameter than the left.

Thus, the right internal Jugular is easier for catheterization [1]. In acute and critical care resuscitation, the CVC is frequently indicated for patients who are being managed with vasoactive or phlebosclerotic medicines that may not be appropriately managed with a peripheral intravenous

alone or for patients who have restricted peripheral access and several incompatible IV drugs [2].

In healthcare settings, Central line-associated bloodstream Infection (CLABSI) is a serious concern, and this infection can lead to increased rates of illness and mortality, along with increased hospital stay [3]. Central line handling consists of several phases. Initially, it starts with insertion, then management, and lastly, line removal. These phases are designed to minimize the risk of central line complications, typically in the subclavian, jugular, or femoral. These critical phases require strict adherence to sterile techniques to prevent infection [2].

Nurses also play a critical role in the early detection and management of complications, ensuring the best possible outcomes for patients with central venous catheterization [4]. In ICUs, the patients are at a greater risk of CLABSI. After multiple insertion attempts. Different types of catheters are exclusively inserted in ICUs, like pulmonary artery catheters with catheter introducers. These catheters have a significant effect on patients' health. These catheters are frequently inserted in an emergency, repeatedly accessed daily, and frequently required for an extended period [5].

As a healthcare provider, it is vital to provide safe patient care. Most importantly, critical care nurses should be able to monitor the patient's overall state, and nurses should also understand the catheter selection and the site selection for insertion, maintenance, and removal [6].

Moreover, the central line care bundles have been updated periodically by the CDC, and the most recent

updated bundles are divided into two major categories: the line insertion bundle and the line maintenance bundles. Insertion bundles that are followed during central line insertion include proper hand hygiene, use of maximum barriers (personal protective equipment), 2% chlorhexidine in 70% alcohol for scrubbing the site, and optimal site selection, preferably in are veins of the neck [7]. The line maintenance bundle includes five moments of hand hygiene as per World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines, an aseptic technique for accessing and changing needleless connectors, standardized tubing change, and a daily review of catheter necessity [7].

Furthermore, after inserting the Central Line, a patient needs hemodynamic Stability, Multiple sampling, assessment of hypovolemia, long-term intravenous medication, and hemodialysis. However, central lines have many disadvantages; the most common disadvantage is central line bloodstream infection (CLABSI). This is the leading issue in critical areas, including the length of Stay (LOS), extra charges, and an increase in mortality and morbidity [8].

As a primary health care provider, a nurse's vital role is to provide safe patient care. Most importantly, critical care Nurses should be able to monitor the patient's overall health state and understand catheter selection and the site selection for insertion, maintenance, and removal [9].

Author	Country	Study Design	Results	Conclusion
(Burt and Spowart, 2021)	United kingdom	Interventional Study	83% central line bloodstream infection reduced by implementing the educational programs.	Hence, it is necessary to conduct interventional study among nurses to enhance the patient's outcome.
(Pareek et al., 2018)	India	Cross-sectional Study	The post-test was increase in experimental group as compared to control group.	Study concluded that planned teaching program (PTP) is necessary for nurses for better performance in

				central line handling.
(Azlan and Aung, 2021).	Malaysia	Cross-sectional Study	100% response rate was achieved and 94.2% of ICU nurses have a good level of knowledge, and 94.2% have a good attitude in handling patients with CVC at ICU. Moreover, 88.4% of participants had good practices based on evidence-based practice guidelines of CVC care.	Hence, the researcher suggested that direct observation checklists should be applied in accessing their practice for future study to reduce the bias.
(Abdo et al., 2020).	Kuwait	Interventional Study	The correct knowledge items regarding care and maintenance of CVCs and prevention of CRBSIs ranged from 31% to 100% and practice items ranged from 0% to 100% at the pre-intervention phase. Significant improvement in all aspects and the total mean scores of the knowledge (10.75±2.59 to 13.43±1.87, $p < 0.001$) and practice (23.72±1.62 to 26.28±1.40, $p < 0.001$) regarding care and maintenance of CVCs was observed among the participants in the post intervention phase after	The implemented educational intervention program improved nurses' knowledge and practice about CVCs maintenance and care of dialysis patient. Provision of continuous and regular bed side training is a good alternative for those who cannot attend the prescheduled formal training.

			implementation of the educational program.	
(George et al., 2019)	India	Interventional Study	The study findings showed that the mean post-test score was higher than the mean pre-test score in the study group	The central line care practice guideline can be used as an effective tool for the maintenance of central venous catheters among children.
(Saggu et al., 2018).	Pakistan	Descriptive cross sectional	Among total of 50 participants, all were female. 40% nurses were university graduates having Post RN degree. All participant nurses (100%) stated that hand hygiene was necessary to prevent infection but none of them (0%) washed hands prior and after the various procedures that demand hand washing. On the other hand, all of them (100%) wore gloves prior or after CVC manipulation. The study revealed that majority of the participants had unsatisfactory level of knowledge and practices (92% and 80% respectively) indicated by total knowledge and practice scores less than 75%.	The results of the current study revealed nurses' low level of knowledge and practices. Therefore, hospitals are required to organize adequate trainings and to develop unit specific clinical guidelines and protocols.

(REHMAN, et al., 2020)	Pakistan	Cross-sectional observational study	<p>82.7% participants' ages were between 21-30 years, 13.5% were between 31-40 years and 3.8% were between 41-50 years. Participants' education was as follows: general nursing diploma (84.2%), BS Nursing Post RN (registered nurse)(11.3%), BSN-Bachelor Science in Nursing (Generic)(4.5%). Only 41.4% participants performed hand hygiene before procedure and 58.6% did not perform. 34.6% participants remove gloves and perform hand hygiene; remaining 65.4% did not perform hand hygiene correctly</p>	<p>The significance of quality care, combined with good practices, particularly when medicines are administered through the Central Venous Catheter. Incorrect practices of medication administration through CVC increase the risk of blood stream infection. This research study shows 50% unsatisfactory practices. Hence it is necessary that Nurse-Led intervention should be done to enhance the patient's caring.</p>
(Shahbaz, K., et al., 2024)	Pakistan	Descriptive cross-sectional Study	<p>The study included 200 nurses, predominantly female (90%), with ages ranging from 18 to 37 years (mean age 25 ± 3.9 years). Professional experience varied, with 36.5% having 1-5 years, 41% having 6-10 years, and 22.5% having 11-15 years of experience (mean experience 7.31 ± 3.0 years). Knowledge assessment revealed that 68.5% knew CVCs should be</p>	<p>While nurses demonstrated satisfactory knowledge regarding central line infection, their practices were inadequate, indicating a need for enhanced nurse-led intervention training and adherence to infection prevention protocols.</p>

			<p>routinely replaced, and 88.5% were aware of disinfecting catheter insertion sites with 10% povidone-iodine. However, only 43% regularly performed hand hygiene before inserting a central line, and 48.5% used chlorhexidine for skin preparation</p>	
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Methods and Material: A comprehensive literature search was conducted across multiple databases, including CINHALL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Science Direct. Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT) and a publication date filter from 2018 to 2025 were applied. Studies were included if they examined nurses performing central line handling in different critical hospital areas. Studies were excluded if published before 2018 or if participants were health care providers other than nurses. Eligible studies were interventional or cross-sectional studies.

Results: The reviewed literature consistently indicates that Nurse-led interventions have shown significant positive impacts on patient outcomes during central line handling, including improved patient safety, improved care coordination, & also improved evidence-based practice (Ball and Singh, 2022) (George et al., 2019).

Limitation:

Variation in study design, sample size, focus on limited outcomes, limited exploration of barriers and facilitators in clinical setting, long term efficacy. These limitations highlight the need for further research to address the complexities of implementing and sustaining nurse-led interventions in various healthcare settings.

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